

THE ROLE OF GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10389660>

Annotation. The article examines the problem of using board games in the process of teaching military history in an educational organization, identifies the advantages and disadvantages of gaming technologies, and describes the real possibilities of using board games in teaching.

Key words: methods of teaching military history, gaming technologies, board games, teaching methods, general education organization.

The problem of using games in the process of teaching military history in an educational organization is very relevant, since in modern conditions the higher military school as a social institution faces an important task - the formation of a comprehensively developed personality of the cadet. Interactive forms of classes are aimed at the multifaceted development of a person, forming a number of competencies necessary in the modern world.

The implementation of interactive learning technologies in modern education is today one of the direct requirements of education throughout the world. This, in turn, places emphasis on the development of soft skills, which are most effectively developed in interactive learning formats. The need to carry out activities to introduce historical games into the training process of cadets lies in personal results, which states that they should reflect:

- 1) awareness of civic identity;
- 2) students' readiness for self-development, independence and personal self-determination;
- 3) the value of independence and initiative;
- 4) presence of motivation for purposeful socially significant activities;
- 5) the formation of the individual's internal position as a special value attitude towards oneself, surrounding people and life in general;

Organizing interactive activities in the format of board games in military history classes is an excellent opportunity not only to develop the teacher, but also to obtain the knowledge and skills necessary for a person to live in society, as well as to develop his motivation for learning and development.

The skillful use of gaming technologies in the learning process contributes to the formation of cognitive, communicative and regulatory skills in students, and, in addition, creates a positive emotional background of the lesson. L.S. Vygotsky imagined the game as a space for "internal socialization" of the student and a means of mastering social attitudes. [3, p. 127]

Before considering the concept of gaming technology, it is worth defining the concept of "game". This definition is presented by G.K. Selevko, who in his work "Modern Educational

Technologies” writes that a game is a type of activity in situations aimed at recreating and assimilating social experience, in which self-control of behavior is formed and improved.

In a modern higher military school, which relies on the activation and intensification of the educational process, gaming technology is used in the following cases:

- ▣as independent technologies for mastering a concept, topic and even a section of an academic subject;

- ▣as elements (sometimes very significant) of a broader technology;

- ▣as a technology of a lesson or its fragment (introduction, explanation, reinforcement, exercise, control);

- ▣as a technology for extracurricular activities.

The essence of the game is to create an entertaining conditional situation, thanks to which the activity acquires a playful character. Therefore, it is advisable to divide games based on how this convention is achieved. L.P. Borzova [2, p. 78] offers three classifications of games:

- on an essential gaming basis;

- on the structural elements of the lesson;

- and on interdisciplinary connections.

The need to use gaming technologies is determined by the presence of a number of functions in the game that have a positive effect on the entire learning process:

- ▣Entertaining. This is one of the main functions of the game, since it is designed to bring joy to the learner and satisfy his needs for leisure and cognition.

- ▣Communicative. This function is aimed at the cadet mastering the ability to communicate with other participants in the game and developing the dialectics of communication.

- ▣Self-realization. The game allows the cadet not only to express himself in various fields, but also to gain an invaluable skill in practical activities.

- ▣Therapeutic. The game is aimed at overcoming difficult life situations by the cadet.

- ▣Socialization function. With the help of the game, the cadet gains sociocultural experience of the society in which he develops and applies all the acquired knowledge in practice.

- ▣Diagnostic. The game allows the teacher to diagnose students' knowledge, as well as identify the psychological characteristics of future officers.

- ▣Motivational. The game awakens the student's interest in the subject or problem being studied, which increases the student's overall motivation for learning and knowledge.

It is worth considering that the use of games in lessons is determined by the age characteristics of the students. So it is worth distinguishing the features of using the game at the highest military educational level.

After analyzing the methodological literature, we can come to the following conclusion that the use of gaming technologies has both significant advantages and disadvantages:

1. Advantages: increased motivation and interest; student activation; development of responsibility and so on.

2. Disadvantages: difficulty in organization and control; the need for a lot of time; difficulty in assessment.

Thus, we can say that gaming technologies are one of the effective elements of interactive learning, which allows not only to qualitatively master the necessary material and develop the

skills of students, but also provides an educational component of the educational process. Through the game, the future officer educates himself and the students around him, tries on various social norms, learns about the world and moral values.

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